

THE ROLE OF STATUS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF A STUDENT'S PERSONALITY

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Annotation: *In this article, opinions are expressed about the role of status in the formation of students as a person in interpersonal relationships, which plays an important role in its development.*

Key words: *Person, student, status, motivation, personality traits.*

An important moment of characterizing a person as a person, his dynamic characteristics are calculated and expressed through his status in society (economic, political, legal, ideological, i.e., his status in society). Status is based on a system of constant interactions. The social function of the role is the orientation to certain goals and values that activates the individual. Orientation to status, role, and value are primary characteristics of a person and serve as a basis for its structure. The definition of the personality determines the characteristics of behavioral motivation and the structure of social character, and takes a place as secondary symptoms in its composition. Human character and inclinations arise in a highly effective manner that combines the interaction of the primary and secondary qualities of a person. The main form that develops the personality of a student is his life path in society and his social biography. It is necessary to pay attention to the following situations in the study of the development of an individual, a person and a subject: - factors and conditions that are considered the basis of human development (social, economic, political, legal, educational, pc-pedagogical and living environment factors); — the main characteristics of the person himself, his internal laws, mechanisms, stage of evolution, stabilization and evolution; - the main components of the human whole structure, the mutual relations of the system, the response and attitude of the person to external influences, the improvement of the system in the process of development, etc

The components of the research program with three different characteristics are the criteria for the practical and theoretical activity of a person. Because in the activity, the living environment is internalized and exteriorized in acquiring the historical experience. In the process of a person's goal-oriented socially useful activity, the so-called vital mechanisms and processes of the functional system of conscious activity arise. Thanks to this, a person not only acquires knowledge, skills and abilities, social experiences, but also his perception, thinking, imagination, emotions and will, in a

word, his conscious attitude to reality and his It contains the motives of z's actions and behavior. All characteristics, attitudes and behaviors of a person are combined into four functional stages, each of which plays a certain role in a person's life and consists of complex devices: First - management system; The second is the stimulation system; The third is the stabilization system; The fourth is the indication system. All these qualities of a person with social significance determine the behavior and actions of a person as a highly conscious worker of social development. The phylogenetic mechanisms that reflect the constant natural connection between analyzers play a major role in the formation of the first system. However, as we mentioned above, in the process of ontogenesis, the connection between phylogenetic analyzers is organically combined with temporal connections. In this case, within this system, a highly integrated m aiium forms an internal sensory complex that passes into the perceptual system. Such complexes include speech, hearing, vision and sensorimotor complexes. All these complexes are in constant contact with each other in the course of a person's life, creating a single functional dynamic system of sensory-perceptive organization. Sensory-perceptive aspects of a person are constantly improving. The second system includes a stable mental state. These situations begin to form in the first years of the child's learning as a conscious subject of a purposeful and useful activity. Temperament, intelligence, knowledge and attitude are among such traits. The third system is the system of stabilization of the person as a character. Orientation, ability, independence and character are its components. Orientation is expressed in the unity of knowledge, attitude, and motivation, where social importance leads the behavior and actions of a person. This characteristic is manifested in a person's worldview, interest, and spiritual needs. Ideological belief plays a major role in the orientation structure. Ideological belief is a synthesis of knowledge, intellectual, emotional and will qualities characteristic of that person, the basis of unity of ideas and actions. The fourth system includes such characteristics, attitudes and behavior that reflect the social "thoughts and feelings" of a real personality. They determine the behavior of these individuals as politically conscious, responsible figures of social development. This includes the qualities of humanism, collectivism, optimism and hard work.

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